

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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STUDYING ORIGINS OF MEDICAL TERMS

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ANNOTATION:

The article is aimed at the history of studying the medical terms as well as illustrating with the brief origin of some specific medical terms. It is recommended to use the written article at medical organizations, as without knowing the main medical terms, it is difficult to be aware of medicine.

Keywords: Word formation, semantic relationship, metaphorization and metonymization, terminologist, homonym, compoundings.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИЯ МЕДИЦИНСКИХ ТЕРМИНОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ:

Статья направлена на историю изучения медицинских терминов, а также на краткую иллюстрацию происхождения некоторых конкретных медицинских терминов. Написанную статью рекомендуется использовать в медицинских организациях, так как без знания основных медицинских терминов сложно ориентироваться в медицине.

Ключевые слова: Словообразование, семантическая связь, метафоризация и метонимизация, терминолог, омонимия, словосложения.

One of the main problems in studying a term is its definition. Over a long period of understanding the features of the term, quite a lot of its definitions have accumulated. All scientists are unanimous that the most important feature of a term is its designation of a scientific concept. Unlike the commonly used word, the “*term*” is based on a special professional concept: G.O. Vinokur , V.P. Danilenko B.N. Golovin , M.N. Volodina and others. Many linguists in terminology works provide various criteria for distinguishing between a commonly used word and a term: B.N. Golovin , V.P. Danilenko , D.S. Lotte, L.M. Alekseeva , L.Yu. Buyanova , S.V. Grinev-Grinevich and others.

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According to B.N. Golovin, “terms do not exist on their own, they are constituent elements of the terminology system”. The terminological system is characterized by the main features: integrity, relative stability, structure, coherence: T.R. Kiyak, S.D. Shelov , A.V. Superanskaya and others. Terminology as an independent science began to take shape in the early 80s of the twentieth century, when quite a lot of works devoted to the study of terms appeared in lexicology. In Russian linguistics, there are a large number of scientific works devoted to various terminologies: military (Kozhin, Sorokoletov) and others, agricultural (Safyan) (Smirnova, Dankova) and others, sports (Kozhevnikova, Gureeva and others), economic (Nazarenko, Davletukaeva, Fedorova) etc.

Recently, interest in the study of Medical Terminology has increased, which is associated with a general interest in the study of individual terminologies. In addition, the study of Medical Terminology is driven by the need to represent it in the form of an ordered system. Most modern linguists show interest in studying modern medical terms of various branches of medicine as an integral part of terminology: G.A. Abramova “Medical vocabulary: main properties and development trends”, E.V. Smirnova “Structural-semantic and lexicographical aspects of medical terminology: using the example of cardiological vocabulary”, E.P. Timoshchuk “Compound anatomical term in modern Russian language”, T.A. Trafimenkova “Terminology of diseases as an object of onomasiological, semantic-paradigmatic and lexicographic research”, N.N. Maslova “Structural-semantic analysis and systematicity of the constituent terms of cardiology and pulmonology (names of diseases and pathological processes” , etc.. In modern works within the framework of terminology, there is an interest in studying the history of various terminologies: A. Sh. Davletukaeva “Diachronic aspect development of economic terminology”, M.V. Tokareva “Formation, development and current state of English terminology of nephrology and urology” , E.V. Korovushkina “Development of credit and financial terminology in the Russian language of the second half of the 19th century” the beginning of the 20th century: semasiological and system-structural aspects" , etc.

The terms of each individual terminology, including medical terminology, largely depend on the properties of OAS terminology, one of which is systematic. Features of the development of terminology are determined, as it were, two-way - both by the properties of the terminology and the specificity of the terms. The

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systematic nature of terminology is organically connected with its development. This unity ensures the identification of trends in the functioning of terminology: a tendency to intensify the process of borrowing, to the internationalization of vocabulary, its interaction with various lexical layers, to complicate the composition of terminology, a tendency towards nominalization, rationalization and saving of linguistic means, differentiation, integration, intellectualization and specialization. These abovementioned trends are manifested primarily in the quantitative development of terminology. The number of medical terms is increasing. The processes of borrowing and word formation play an important role here.

Foreign language vocabulary had a significant influence on the formation of German medical terminology in all periods of its existence. In the modern era of its development, tendencies towards the internationalization of languages and the intensification of borrowing processes appear especially clearly. Borrowings have different genetic origins, but the largest class consists of terms that came from the English language, which is due to both extralinguistic reasons and the high prestige of the English language throughout the world.

The international nature of medical science predetermines the process of internationalization of borrowings, however, most internationalisms in German medical terminology were created on a Greco-Latin basis. Similar to native German medical terms, borrowed terms may exhibit semantic processes associated with changes in their scope of meaning. There are some medical term are given to illustrate the given sentences:

-Anatomy: Origin: Greek "anatome" (dissection); (- "Ana") means "up" and "tome" means "cutting," referring to the dissection process to study body structures.

-Cardiology: Origin: Greek "kardia" (heart) + "logos" (study). As it is known, This term refers to the study of the heart and its functions.

-Dermatology: Origin: Greek "derma" (skin) + "logos" (study); It is the branch of medicine dealing with the skin and its diseases.

-Neurology: Origin: Greek "neuron" (nerve) + "logos" (study); this field focuses on the nervous system and its disorders.

-Ophthalmology: Origin: Greek "ophthalmos" (eye) + "logos" (study); this term refers to the medical specialty concerning the eye and its diseases.

-Pediatrics: Origin: Greek "pais" (child) + "iatros" (doctor); this field deals with the medical care of infants, children, and adolescents.

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-Psychiatry: Origin: Greek "psyche" (mind) + "iatros" (doctor); It involves the study and treatment of mental illnesses.

-Surgery: Origin: Greek "cheir" (hand) + "ergon" (work); Refers to the branch of medicine that treats diseases and injuries by operative procedures.

-Pathology: Origin: Greek "pathos" (disease) + "logos" (study); The study of diseases, their causes, and effects.

-Gynecology: Origin: Greek "gyne" (woman) + "logos" (study); This field focuses on the health of the female reproductive system.

As it is proved that, most medical terms are derived from Greek and Latin roots, reflecting the historical dominance of these languages in science and medicine. Greek roots often refer to the body part involved, while Latin terms frequently describe the condition or the procedure. Understanding the etymology of medical terms not only aids in grasping their meanings but also helps in learning and remembering them more effectively. Along with borrowing, word formation is a powerful source of development of German medical terminology. It is closely related to the tendency towards linguistic economy in signs conveying the content of an utterance, which is also inherent in the special vocabulary of the German language. This trend is expressed in the widespread use of elliptical structures and various kinds of abbreviations.

Word formation is the most characteristic way of development of German medical terminology, which is explained by the peculiarities of the structure of the German language. Abbreviation has become one of the most productive means of forming new terms. However, the most productive means of forming terminology is compounding (basic compounding). Trends towards the internationalization of vocabulary and the integration of languages explain the widespread use of cripple terms and eponym terms in German medical terminology. During their formation, the semantics (and structure) of the term are borrowed, although its material shell is built on the basis of the German language. Word-forming tracing papers filled German medical terminology at all stages of its development. This trend continues in our time. An equally important way of replenishing terminology with new terms is the formation of eponymous terms, which, despite intensive measures to eliminate them, continue to actively function.

Along with this, the terminology is replenished with words from commonly used vocabulary. Its replenishment with linguistic means of the national language

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occurs mainly through *metaphorization and metonymization*. These semantic processes contribute to the development of *polysemy and homonymy*.

Polysemy is a semantic relationship of internally related (motivated) meanings expressed by the forms of one word and creating a certain system. The presence of polysemy in terminology suggests that the tendency towards unambiguity of lexical units is inferior to the tendency towards expanding the scope of their semantic content. The difference between polysemy and homonymy in medical terminology is established using the method of semantic analysis, as well as auxiliary criteria - grammatical and word-formation. Despite the fact that lexicologists and terminologists-normalizers are constantly fighting against such phenomena as synonymy and polysemy, the latter inevitably accompanies term formation. These semantic phenomena can neither be ignored nor overcome, since it is impossible to separate the term from the real living linguistic matter.

In conclusion, all semantic processes are subject to its linguistic laws, determined by the systematic nature of the lexical level of language. In particular, manifests itself in the relationships between the meanings of terms, which change with the development of terminology. No matter how different the meanings of a particular medical term may be, there is something in common that maintains their unity within the system. It lies in a certain connection of values with each other. When identifying these connections, it is necessary to rely on the underlying meaning.

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